

APPENDIX S1

Journal Name: Ecology

Manuscript Type: Article

Title: Developmental plasticity does not improve performance during a species interaction: implications for species turnover along environmental gradients.

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A)

Experimental Design

B)

Ecological Scenarios

Figure S1: A) A diagram of the experimental design for the competition experiments. *P. reticulata* competed against *P. picta* of freshwater (0psu) or brackish water (15psu) origin (blue or green *P. picta* icons, respectively) in interspecific competition treatments or against other *P. reticulata* in intraspecific competition treatments. Competition trials took place in either freshwater or brackish water (blue or yellow-green background shading, respectively). *P.*

reticulata were developed in either freshwater (0psu) or brackish water (30psu) (blue or green *P. reticulata* icons, respectively). The salinity transfer experienced by each fish in each treatment is shown above each fish. The sample size for each type of interaction is shown above double-sided arrows. **B)** A short description of the ecological scenarios represented by the experimental treatments described in panel A. Although each treatment was useful in creating a balanced design and teasing apart our main factors, the scenarios highlighted in yellow are those that are most ecologically relevant. Specifically, the scenarios that modeled performance at the current range limit or that modeled interspecific competition after an attempted colonization of brackish water were deemed most ecologically relevant because these scenarios are most helpful when trying to explain the current distribution of *P. reticulata* in nature.

Figure S2: The average total aggressive behaviors per interaction (on the log scale) for *P. picta* in either fresh (F) or brackish (B) acute salinities when competing against *P. reticulata* from either the freshwater developed group (left two bars) or brackish water developed group (right two bars). There was an overall effect of *P. picta* displaying more aggressive behaviors when competing against brackish developed *P. reticulata*. Means with 95% confidence intervals are displayed. See Table S13 for statistical results.

Table. S1. ANOVA table for the effect of environmental salinity, species, food level, the interaction between food level & salinity, and the interaction between salinity & species on the growth rate of both *P. reticulata* and *P. picta*.

Factor	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDf	DenDF	F-value	P-value
Species	0.360	0.360	1	55.757	0.6532	0.4224
Salinity	16.980	16.980	1	231.806	30.8313	<0.0001
Food	260.738	130.369	2	217.801	236.6785	<0.0001
Species:Salinity	5.765	5.765	1	231.806	10.4681	0.0014
Species:Food	0.774	0.387	2	217.801	0.7024	0.4965
Salinity:Food	7.262	3.631	2	212.823	6.5921	0.0017
Species:Salinity:Food	0.356	0.178	2	212.823	0.3229	0.7243

Table. S2. Least-squared means contrasts for the model from Table S1. We contrasted environmental salinities (Brackish – Freshwater) at each food level for both species using a Tukey adjustment for multiple comparisons.

Contrast	Species	Food Level	Estimate	SE	df	T-ratio	P-value
B-F	Picta	High	0.122	0.227	227	0.539	0.5906
B-F	Picta	Medium	-0.216	0.217	217	-0.993	0.3218
B-F	Picta	Low	-0.670	0.359	232	-1.868	0.0631
B-F	Ret	High	-0.375	0.210	221	-1.784	0.0757
B-F	Ret	Medium	-0.903	0.205	214	-4.396	<0.0001
B-F	Ret	Low	-1.619	0.329	219	-4.918	<0.0001

Table. S3. Least-squared means estimates from the model from Table S1. Confidence intervals are 95% confidence intervals.

Species	Food Level	Salinity	Estimate	SE	df	Lower CI	Upper CI
Picta	High	B	8.63	0.173	188	8.28	8.97
Picta	High	F	8.50	0.163	198	8.18	8.82
Picta	Medium	B	6.88	0.167	197	6.55	7.21
Picta	Medium	F	7.09	0.158	188	6.78	7.40
Picta	Low	B	5.49	0.275	230	4.95	6.03
Picta	Low	F	6.16	0.236	228	5.70	6.63
Ret	High	B	8.41	0.155	182	8.11	8.72
Ret	High	F	8.79	0.159	180	8.47	9.10
Ret	Medium	B	6.49	0.160	197	6.18	6.81
Ret	Medium	F	7.40	0.148	177	7.11	7.69
Ret	Low	B	4.71	0.216	230	4.28	5.14
Ret	Low	F	6.33	0.258	232	5.82	6.84

Table. S4. ANOVA table for the effect of environmental salinity, developmental salinity and competition on the change in body condition in *P. reticulata*. Environmental salinity (salinity), developmental salinity (dev), competition (comp) and all possible interactions were treated as fixed factors and family, and tank were treated as random factors.

Factor	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDf	DenDF	F-value	P-value
Salinity	3.08E-03	3.08E-03	1	33.860	5.72E-01	0.45488
Dev	6.12E-02	6.12E-02	1	33.335	1.13E+01	0.00193
Comp	5.38E-05	5.38E-05	1	34.718	9.97E-03	0.92106
Salinity:Dev	5.21E-03	5.21E-03	1	34.385	9.65E-01	0.33285
Salinity:Comp	3.11E-02	3.11E-02	1	34.282	5.77E+00	0.02188
Dev:Comp	4.33E-03	4.33E-03	1	33.964	8.02E-01	0.37684
Salinity:Dev:Comp	2.52E-06	2.52E-06	1	33.863	4.67E-04	0.98289

Table. S5. Least-squared means contrasts for the model from Table S4. Within each level of development (Fresh (F) or Brackish (B)) and competition (interspecific or intraspecific), environmental salinity (Fresh (F) - Brackish (B)) were contrasted with a Tukey adjustment for multiple comparisons.

Comp Level	Dev Level	Contrast (Salinity)	Estimate	SE	Df	T-ratio	P-value
Inter	F	F-B	0.1500	0.0647	42.7	2.319	0.0253
Inter	B	F-B	0.0816	0.0805	42.8	1.014	0.3165
Intra	F	F-B	-0.0247	0.0732	27.1	-0.338	0.7380
Intra	B	F-B	-0.0963	0.0695	27.8	-1.385	0.1771

Table. S6. Least-squared means estimates from the model from Table S4. Confidence intervals are 95% confidence intervals.

Dev	Comp	Salinity	Lsmean	SE	Df	Lower CI	Upper CI
Fresh	Inter	F	0.1028	0.0427	41.6	0.0167	0.1890
Fresh	Inter	B	-0.0472	0.0489	42.2	-0.1459	0.0515
Brackish	Inter	F	-0.0820	0.0533	42.8	-0.1896	0.0256
Brackish	Inter	B	-0.1636	0.0593	42.8	-0.2832	-0.0439
Fresh	Intra	F	-0.0129	0.0399	26.8	-0.0949	0.0691
Fresh	Intra	B	0.0118	0.0609	27.1	-0.1131	0.1368
Brackish	Intra	F	-0.1355	0.0528	27	-0.2438	-0.0271
Brackish	Intra	B	-0.0392	0.0444	28.5	-0.1302	0.0518

Table. S7. ANOVA table for the effect of developmental salinity (family was a random factor) on the starting body condition of the *P. reticulata* used in body condition and behavior experiments.

Factor	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDf	DenDF	F-value	P-value
Dev Salinity	8.2699e-05	8.2699e-05	1	51.349	0.3527	0.5552

Table. S8. ANOVA table for the effect of environmental salinity on the difference in aggressive behaviors between pairs of *P. reticulata* and *P. picta*. Environmental salinity (salinity), developmental salinity (Dev), and their interaction were treated as a fixed factors and family were treated as random factors.

Factor	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDf	DenDF	F-value	P-value
Dev	38.475	38.475	1	17.232	0.8441	0.3709
Salinity	9.551	9.551	1	18.719	0.2095	0.6524
Dev:Salinity	54.94	54.94	1	18.671	1.2053	0.2862

Table. S9. ANOVA table for the effect of environmental salinity on the difference in aggressive behaviors between pairs of *P. reticulata* and *P. picta*. Data was split by development (Freshwater (F) or Brackish water (B)) and separate models were run for each data set. Environmental salinity (salinity) was treated as a fixed factor and family was treated as a random factor in the freshwater developed model whereas family was not included in the brackish developed model because of a lack of observations

Factor	Dev	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDf	DenDF	F-value	P-value
Salinity	F	75.888	75.888	1	8.6535	16.743	0.002944
Factor	Dev	Sum Sq		Df		F-value	P-value
Salinity	B	7.36		1		0.0673	0.8028
Residuals	B	765.66		7			

Table. S10. Least-squared means estimates from the models from Table S8. Confidence intervals are 95% confidence intervals.

Dev	Salinity	Lsmean	SE	Df	Lower CI	Upper CI
Fresh	F	0.318	1.49	14	-2.87	3.51
Fresh	B	-6.122	1.46	13	-9.06	-3.19
Brackish	F	-6.86	4.68	7	-17.9	4.2
Brackish	B	-5.04	5.23	7	-17.4	7.33

Table. S11. ANOVA table for the effect of environmental salinity and mass difference between *P. reticulata* and its *P. picta* competitor on the difference in aggressive behaviors between each fish pair. Separate models were run for each *P. reticulata* developmental group (Brackish (B) and Freshwater (F)).

Factor	Dev	Sum Sq	Df	F-value	P-value
Mass Difference	B	105.54	1	0.9488	0.8878
Salinity	B	15.07	1	0.1367	0.7242
Residuals	B	661.12	6		
Mass Difference	F	0.816	1	0.0605	0.80991
Salinity	F	85.029	1	6.2997	0.02741
Residuals	F	161.969	12		

Table. S12. ANOVA output table for the effect of competition, environmental salinity, developmental salinity (dev), and all possible two-way interactions on total aggressive behavior counts in *P. reticulata*.

Factor	Chisquare	Df	P-value
Development	0.8100	1	0.36812
Comp	4.5962	1	0.03204
Salinity	0.0112	1	0.91561
Development:Comp	0.7852	1	0.37555
Comp:Salinity	0.0114	1	0.91491
Development:Salinity	3.5338	1	0.06013

Table S13: ANOVA output table for the effect of acute salinity, developmental salinity of *P. reticulata* competitor (Dev_reticulata), and their interactions on total aggressive behavior counts in *P. picta*. To conduct this analysis, we used a generalized linear mixed model in which the average total aggression count per interaction was a response, acute salinity, developmental salinity of *P. reticulata* and their interaction were fixed factors, and family was a random factor using the glmer function in R (distribution=Poisson, link=log).

Factor	Chisquare	Df	P-value
Acute Salinity	2.3182	1	0.12786
Dev_reticulata	5.1860	1	0.02277
Salinity:Dev_reticulata	0.0547	1	0.81514

Section S1: Collection date/location and experimental timeline

Experiment (group)	Collection Date	Collection Location	Experiment Date
Growth Rate (<i>P. reticulata</i> & <i>P. picta</i>)	Spring 2011	10.619250, -61.426492	June 2011-April 2012
Competition (<i>P. reticulata</i> & freshwater <i>P. picta</i>)	March/April 2016 & August 2017	10.619250, -61.426492	May/June 2019
Competition (Brackish water <i>P. picta</i>)	March/April 2016 & August 2017	10.6053117, -61.4247778	May/June 2019

Section S2: Body Condition Measurement Protocol

Body condition was calculated from length and mass using the “scaled mass index” equation suggested by Peig and Green (2009, 2010) in which each individual’s mass is scaled to the length of the individual as well as the population average of mass and length (the unit of the scaled mass index retains the original mass units). Length and mass measurements were taken by first anesthetizing the fish with a dose of MS-222 and then weighing (in grams) and photographing the fish. Length (in mm) was derived from the photo using ImageJ. After anesthetization, fish recovered in their test salinities for 1hr before re-entering competition tanks. Baseline body condition was calculated from length and mass measurements taken 48hrs prior to

the start of the study. Body condition change from that baseline was then calculated weekly on days 7,14, 21 after behavioral observations.

Section S3: Ethogram

1. **Nip:** “An individual bites or attempts to bite its opponent. The nipped fish often makes a rapid retreat.” (Magurran and Seghers 1991)
2. **Rapid Approach or Chase (RA/Chase):** “An individual swims rapidly towards an opponent, usually aiming at its flank and may attempt to nip it. The attacked guppy usually responds by fleeing” (Magurran and Seghers 1991)
3. **Guarding or Patch Monopoly (PM):** “Individual actively defends patch and chases/herds all other foragers away” (Magurran and Seghers 1991). This behavior is characterized by the individual facing its opponent and putting itself between the patch and its opponent while following the opponent’s movement.
4. **Tail Beating (TB):** During tail-beating a guppy lashes its tail toward the flank of its opponent.
5. **Gonopodium Swing (GPS):** An individual swings its gonopodium toward an opponent
6. **Fin Flare (FF):** An individual flares either its dorsal or tail fin while facing its opponent or directly after a conflict.

References Cited

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